

Supplementary Table 1. Overview of the participants and the saliva samples in the three sub-studies.

	Liquorice	Topical hydrocortisone	Blood contamination
No. of participants initially recruited	30	30	16
No. of participants after exclusion	26	28	16
No. of females (%)	12 (46.2)	13 (46.4)	8 (50)
Age range, y	22–53	22–55	24–50
Time of sampling	22:00–23:00 h (and 06:00–08:00 h)	13:00–17:00 h	07:00–09:00 h
No. of expected samples	806	28+28	16+16
No. of missing samples	29	0	0+0
No. of excluded samples	2	0	0+3
Final no. of samples	776	28+28	16+13